

RESIDUAL EFFECT OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE COMPOST AND FERTILIZER ON THE PERFORMANCE OF TRANSPLANTED AMAN RICE CV. BRR1 dhan31 AFTER BORO RICE

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Abstract

A field experiment was carried out at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the *aman* season of 2010 to study the residual effects of composted Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) and fertilizer on the yield performance of T. *aman* rice cv. BRR1 dhan31. Different levels of the compost and fertilizers were used in *boro* rice which was the previous crop. The experiment in *boro* rice was designed with two factors in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Factor A comprised 4 treatments: 0, 5, 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹ of MSW compost and Factor B with other 4 treatments: 0%, 25%, 50% and 100% of the Recommended Fertilizers (RF). Only the RF rates were applied in all plots of the T. *aman* rice and no compost was used there. The results revealed that the main effects of the compost and fertilizers, and their integrated use had significant influences on the yield and yield contributing characters of T. *aman* rice except thousand grain weight. In case of sole application of MSW compost and fertilizers in the *boro* rice, the residual effect of the compost on T. *aman* rice was in general higher than that of the fertilizer for example, the values for grain yield were 20.36% @ 20 t ha⁻¹ of compost use compared to 11.22% @ 100% RF use. In case of combined effect of MSW compost and fertilizer the grain and straw yield increases were much higher, ranging from 32.55 to 58.9 % and 34.04 to 57.07 %, respectively, over the control. The highest grain and straw yields of 4.93t and 7.25 t ha⁻¹, respectively, were observed in T. *aman* rice, when integrated use of compost and fertilizer was applied in *boro* rice @ 20 t ha⁻¹ of MSW plus 100% RF.

Keywords: MSW compost, Residual effect, T. *aman* rice, Yield.

Introduction

About 77% of the total cropped area of Bangladesh is devoted to rice producing 31.32 million tons of grains in 2008-09 (BBS, 2009). The present average yield of rice in the country is only 2.8 t ha⁻¹ (BBS, 2009), which is very low compared with other rice growing countries. The low yield of rice in Bangladesh may be due to low soil fertility, poor organic matter status, conventional cultivation and the hazards of the climatic aberrations. In Bangladesh, about 40% soils have less than 1.0% organic matter (BARC, 1997). The continuous application of N, P, K and S fertilizers at higher doses due to use of high yielding varieties are exerting a deteriorating effect on soil health. Besides, the area of the cultivable land is decreasing day by day. So, to meet our food demands, emphasis should be given to explore the possibilities of increasing food production unit⁻¹ area using organic matter and soil management. Generation of huge amount of degradable solid waste in the municipality area and their improper management cause various environmental pollution and civic problems. Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) compost would be helpful for environmental management as well as improving soil fertility through direct and residual

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effects on yield performance of different crops. MSW compost gives a relatively stable high rice yield (Miyazaki *et al.*, 1986). The Residual effects of N- or P-based manure or MSW compost application increase crop production for one year and influence soil properties for several years (Eghball *et al.*, 2004). MSW compost is largely made-up of kitchen and yard wastes, and its composting has been adopted by many municipalities. Composting MSW is seen as a method of diverting organic waste materials from the landfills while creating a product, at relatively low-cost, that is suitable for agricultural purposes. In the light of above fact it is utmost necessary to conduct experiments taking different combinations of chemical fertilizers with MSW compost to find out the best suitable combinations of fertilizer with compost in rice cultivation and their direct and residual effects on soil fertility. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken to evaluate the residual effect of sole application of fertilizer and MSW compost, and integrated use of MSW compost and fertilizer on the yield performance of *T. aman* rice cv. BRRI dhan31 following *boro* rice which received different levels of MSW compost and fertilizer.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out at the Agronomy Field Laboratory of the Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from June to December 2010. The soil of the experimental field lies in argo-ecological region of Old Brahmaputra Floodplain (AEZ#9). It belongs to the Sonatola series of the general soil type non-calcareous dark grey floodplain soils. BRRI dhan31, a high yielding variety of *T. aman* rice was used as a test crop in the experiment. Experiment for *boro* rice was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 64 (16x4) unit plots. The plots of the previous *boro* rice experiment were used for the purpose of *T. aman* rice study. Four levels of compost viz. 0, 5, 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹ and another four levels of fertilizer viz. 0, 25, 50 and 100% of the recommended fertilizers Urea, TSP, MOP, Gypsum and Zinc Sulphate @ 200, 50, 85, 45 and 8kg ha⁻¹, respectively (BARC, 2005) were applied in the previous *boro* rice crop. In case of *T. aman* rice only 100% RFs were applied in all plots of the treatment combination of the preceding *boro* experiment. No MSW compost was used in the *T. aman* rice experiment. The land of *T. aman* rice was prepared by only repeated spading maintaining the same plot size of *boro* rice. Five hills were selected at random from each unit plot and uprooted carefully and tagged before harvesting. Data were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique with the help of computer package program and differences were adjudged by Duncan Multiple Range Test. The soil samples were analysed by using Modified Olsen method for phosphorus (P) and N NH₄OAc method for potassium (K) from Soil Resource Development Institute (SRDI) and the Department of Soil Science of Bangladesh Agricultural University.

Results and Discussion

Residual effect of MSW compost

Sole application of MSW compost in *boro* rice have significant residual effect on grain and straw yield, plant height, effective tillers hill⁻¹, grains panicle⁻¹ of *T. aman* rice (Table 1). The residual effect of C₂₀ (20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost) exerted highest grain yield (4.67 tha⁻¹) and straw yield (6.99 t ha⁻¹). The highest value of plant height (113.78 cm) was obtained in *T. aman* rice where 20 tha⁻¹ MSW compost was used in the previous *boro* rice. The treatment C₂₀ gave the highest number of effective tillers (9.8) which was statistically

different with other MSW compost rates. Among the treatments, C₂₀ (20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost) produced the highest number of grains (125.1) panicle⁻¹ which was statistically similar to C₅ and C₁₀. There was no significant residual effect of MSW compost on thousand grain weight of *T. aman* rice.

Table 1: Residual effect of MSW compost after *boro* rice on plant characters and yield of *T. aman* rice

Compost (t ha ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Thousand grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% Increase over control	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% Increase over control
C ₀	104.53c	6.7d	113.0b	22.47	3.88c	-	5.82c	-
C ₅	108.70b	7.5c	121.7a	22.51	4.29b	10.57	6.45b	10.82
C ₁₀	110.96b	8.3b	123.7a	22.55	4.31b	11.08	6.51b	11.86
C ₂₀	113.78a	9.8a	125.1a	22.65	4.67a	20.36	6.99a	20.10
CV (%)	4.43	10.30	7.64	4.21	8.94		8.83	
Level of sig.	**	**	*	NS	**		**	

Rate of compost: C₀ = Control (no compost), C₅ = 5 t ha⁻¹, C₁₀ = 10 t ha⁻¹, and C₂₀ = 20 t ha⁻¹

The above stated results revealed that *T. aman* rice yield including all other plant characters studied produced the highest value on 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost applied in the previous *boro* rice and the value for all parameters decreased gradually with the reduced rate of MSW compost application. This might be due to the deviation of MSW residue from the optimum level to require the highest value that prevails on 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost rate used in the *boro* crop. These results support the previous results of Aga *et al.* (2004), Naklang *et al.* (1999), Meelu and Morris (1987) and Miyazaki *et al.* (1986).

Residual effect of fertilizer

The result showed that the residual effect of fertilizer produced significant response on rice yield (t ha⁻¹) and effective tillers hill⁻¹ of *T. aman* rice (Table 2). The 100% recommended fertilizer rate (F₁₀₀) in previous *boro* rice produced highest grain yield (4.46 t ha⁻¹) of *T. aman* rice. The F₁₀₀ also exerted maximum straw yield (6.66 t ha⁻¹) which was statistically similar to F₅₀. There was positive relationship between increasing fertilizer dose and its residual effect on grain and straw yield of the following crop *T. aman* rice. The effective tiller number hill⁻¹ ranged from 7.6 to 8.5. The treatment F₁₀₀ (100% RF) gave the highest number (8.5) which was statistically similar to F₅₀ and F₂₅. The residual effect was non-significant on plant height, grains panicle⁻¹ and thousand grains wt.(g) of *T. aman* rice due to application of RFs in the preceding *boro* rice.

Table 2: Residual effect of fertilizers after *boro* rice on plant characters and yield of *T. aman* rice

Fertilizer (% Recom. dose)	Plant height (cm)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Thousand grains wt(g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% Increase over control	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% Increase over control
F ₀	108.11	7.6b	117.7	22.14b	4.01d	-	6.03c	-
F ₂₅	109.29	7.9ab	120.7	22.46ab	4.30c	7.23	6.49b	7.63
F ₅₀	109.75	8.3ab	122.1	22.63ab	4.39b	9.48	6.59a	9.29
F ₁₀₀	110.82	8.5a	123.1	22.95a	4.46a	11.22	6.66a	10.45
CV (%)	4.43	10.30	7.64	4.21	8.94		8.83	
Level of sig.	NS	*	NS	NS	**		**	

Rate of fertilizers: F₀ = Control (no fertilizers), F₂₅ = 25% Recommended Fertilizers (RF), F₅₀ = 50% RF, and F₁₀₀ = 100% RF

The residual effect of fertilizer on the rice yield and other plant parameters in our study revealed that among the different rates of fertilizer applied, 100% recommended fertilizer produced the highest value of rice yield including all the plant characters. It may be concluded that the residual effect increases with the increment of percent recommended fertilizer application. This statement supports the previous results of Singh *et al.* (2006) and Zhang *et al.* (2000).

Interaction residual effect of MSW compost and fertilizer on different plant characters

The highest value of plant height (115.365 cm) was observed in *T. aman* rice where 100 % RF and 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost were used in the previous *boro* rice crop (Table 3). The treatment C₂₀F₁₀₀ (100 % RF and 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost) gave the highest number of effective tillers (10.258) hill⁻¹. The maximum panicle length 22.684 cm was recorded in *T. aman* rice because of residual effect of mixed application of 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost and 100% RF in the previous *boro* rice. The minimum panicle length of 20.061 cm was recorded in control treatment. Result shows that the highest number of grains (128.028) panicle⁻¹ in the *T. aman* rice due to application of 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost and 100% RF in the previous *boro* rice.

Table 3: Residual effect of MSW compost and fertilizers on yield components of *T. aman* rice

Treatments	Plant Height (cm)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Thousand grain wt. (g)
C ₀ F ₀	101.587e	6.026g	20.061f	103.874c	21.814b
C ₀ F ₂₅	104.996de	6.387fg	20.330e	112.876b	22.748a
C ₀ F ₅₀	104.815de	7.183efg	20.603d	119.706a	23.442a
C ₀ F ₁₀₀	106.749cde	7.207efg	21.028c	115.627a	21.863a
C ₅ F ₀	107.975bcd	7.387defg	21.334b	123.652a	22.668a
C ₅ F ₂₅	108.113bcd	7.503defg	21.478b	123.103a	22.643a
C ₅ F ₅₀	109.301abcd	7.405defg	21.766a	124.376a	22.347a
C ₅ F ₁₀₀	109.423abcd	7.607defg	21.864a	123.578a	22.405a
C ₁₀ F ₀	110.254abcd	7.759def	21.735a	119.425a	22.024a
C ₁₀ F ₂₅	110.565abcd	8.055cde	21.608a	122.424a	22.387a
C ₁₀ F ₅₀	111.292abc	8.605bcde	21.898a	124.023a	23.492a
C ₁₀ F ₁₀₀	111.757abc	8.857abcd	21.855a	121.107a	22.338a
C ₂₀ F ₀	112.658abc	9.359abc	21.883a	123.709a	22.077a
C ₂₀ F ₂₅	113.499ab	9.723ab	22.247a	124.404a	22.756a
C ₂₀ F ₅₀	113.603ab	9.968ab	22.287a	124.423a	22.536a
C ₂₀ F ₁₀₀	115.365a	10.258a	22.684a	128.028a	23.263a
Cv(%)	4.43	18.3	4.18	7.64	4.21
SE±	0.6061	0.185	0.1125	1.154	0.1187
Level of sig.	***	***	***	*	NS

Note: Rate of compost: C₀ = Control (no compost), C₅ = 5 t ha⁻¹, C₁₀ = 10 t ha⁻¹, and C₂₀ = 20 t ha⁻¹. Rate of fertilizers: F₀ = Control (no fertilizers), F₂₅ = 25% Recommended Fertilizers (RF), F₅₀ = 50% RF and F₁₀₀ = 100% RF.

Figures in a column having common letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter(s) differ significantly as per DMRT. CV (%) = Coefficient of variation, SE (±) = Standard error of means

Interaction residual effect of MSW compost and fertilizer on rice yield

Interaction effect of MSW compost and fertilizer on *T. aman* rice yield was significant (Fig. 1 and 2). A remarkable low grain yield (3.103 t ha^{-1}) was observed in control where no compost and fertilizer were used. The result showed that grain yield of *T. aman* rice increased with the application of more MSW compost and fertilizer in the *boro* rice. The application of 20 t ha^{-1} MSW compost and 100% RF exerted the highest grain yield 4.93 t ha^{-1} . The C_5 and C_{10} with different levels of fertilizer produced statistically similar results. All the treated plots produced 32.55 to 58.9 % higher grain yield over control. Like grain yield, straw yield was also significantly affected by the different treatments. It ranged from 4.61 to 7.25 t ha^{-1} with the increase of 34.04 to 57.07 % over control. The lowest straw yield (4.61 t ha^{-1}) was observed in control (0 t ha^{-1} MSW and 0% RF) although different levels of fertilizer dose without using compost showed statistically similar yields. In comparison with no compost application, the distinctive straw yield was observed in the treatments where 5 t ha^{-1} MSW compost with various doses of fertilizer were used which is showed in (Fig. 2). The maximum straw yield of *T. aman* rice 7.25 t ha^{-1} was recorded in the treatment $C_{20}F_{100}$ (20 t ha^{-1} MSW and 100% RF) and it was statistically identical to the treatment $C_{20}F_{50}$ (20 t ha^{-1} MSW and 50% RF).

Note: Rate of compost: C_0 = Control (no compost), C_5 = 5 t ha^{-1} , C_{10} = 10 t ha^{-1} , and C_{20} = 20 t ha^{-1} . Rate of fertilizers: F_0 = Control (no fertilizers), F_{25} = 25% Recommended Fertilizers (RF), F_{50} = 50% RF, and F_{100} = 100% RF.

Fig. 1. Residual effect of MSW compost and fertilizers on grain yield

Note: Rate of compost: C₀ = Control (no compost), C₅ = 5 t ha⁻¹, C₁₀ = 10 t ha⁻¹, and C₂₀ = 20 t ha⁻¹. Rate of fertilizers: F₀ = Control (no fertilizers), F₂₅ = 25% Recommended Fertilizers (RF), F₅₀ = 50% RF, and F₁₀₀ = 100% RF.

Fig. 2. Residual effect of MSW compost and fertilizers on straw yield
Residual Effect of MSW Compost and Fertilizers on Soil

The different levels of MSW compost and RF were applied in the *boro* rice experiment, which resulted residual effect in the *T. aman* rice soil after harvesting of *boro* rice. The considerable amount of phosphorus (P) was found in soil before transplanting of *T. aman* rice, that was uptaken by the *T. aman* rice (Table 4). There was little residual effect of MSW compost and RFs on increasing potassium (K) in the soil. The negligible amounts of other nutrient elements were found in the soil as residual effect of MSW compost and RFs application.

Table 4: Chemical properties of soil before and after *boro* rice cultivation

Treatments	Chemical properties of soil			
	Before planting of <i>boro</i> rice		After harvesting of <i>boro</i> rice	
	P (µg/g)	K (meq/100g)	P (µg/g)	K (meq/100g)
C ₀ F ₀	27	0.10	26	0.10
C ₀ F ₂₅	24	0.09	17	0.10
C ₀ F ₅₀	24	0.10	18	0.11
C ₀ F ₁₀₀	23	0.13	31	0.13
C ₅ F ₀	26	0.10	18	0.12
C ₅ F ₂₅	30	0.09	20	0.12
C ₅ F ₅₀	28	0.09	27	0.13
C ₅ F ₁₀₀	21	0.11	32	0.14
C ₁₀ F ₀	30	0.10	27	0.14
C ₁₀ F ₂₅	29	0.08	17	0.15
C ₁₀ F ₅₀	28	0.08	45	0.15
C ₁₀ F ₁₀₀	33	0.09	58	0.16
C ₂₀ F ₀	25	0.09	24	0.16
C ₂₀ F ₂₅	28	0.08	21	0.16
C ₂₀ F ₅₀	23	0.20	34	0.17
C ₂₀ F ₁₀₀	24	0.08	50	0.17

Conclusion

The present study revealed that both MSW compost and fertilizer exerted significant residual effect on yield and plant characters of *T. aman* rice. The yield decreased gradually from the highest level with the lowering application of combined MSW compost and fertilizer in the previous *boro* rice crop. The results indicated that the highest *T. aman* yield was obtained from the residual effect of combined application of 20 t ha⁻¹ MSW compost and 100% recommended fertilizers in the *boro* rice. Finally, it may be concluded that the residual effect of MSW and fertilizer proved to be as effective way of increasing yield of *T. aman* rice.

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